

Studies in Thiadiazoles. Part I. Synthesis of Some Substituted Sulphathiadiazoles and Related Compounds

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Several 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been prepared and condensed with acetylsulphanil chloride. The 2-(*N*⁴-acetylsulphanilamido)-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, thus obtained, have been hydrolysed to provide the corresponding 2-sulphanilamidothiadiazoles. The latter have been condensed with phthalic and succinic anhydrides to yield 2-(*N*⁴-phthalyl)- and 2-(*N*⁴-succinyl)-sulphanilamidothiadiazoles respectively.

The replacement of the amido-H of sulphanilamide by heterocyclic moieties has led to the discovery of chemotherapeutically important drugs, like sulphapyridine, sulphadiazine, sulphathiazole, etc. That a similar substitution by a thiadiazole moiety may also yield useful drugs is apparent from the commercialisation of Globucide (I) and Lucosil (II) as the antibacterial drugs¹ and Diamox (III) and allied compounds as the drugs exhibiting diuretic activity of high order²⁻³.

In view of above it was considered worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of substituted sulphathiadiazoles involving variations on thiadiazole nucleus. Further, based on the earlier observation⁴ that certain 2-(*N*⁴-phthalylsulphanilamido)thiadiazoles are useful in the treatment of intestinal bacterial infections, we have also prepared some 2-(*N*⁴-phthalyl)- and 2-(*N*⁴-succinyl)-sulphathiadiazoles, the analogues of sulphaphthalidine (IV) and sulphasuccidine (V) respectively, which are of special value in intestinal bacterial infections, particularly, bacillary dysentery, cholera, and ulcerative colitis⁵.

(I): R = Et.
(II): R = Me.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

1. May, "Chemistry of Synthetic Drugs", Longmans, 5th ed., 1958, p. 491.
2. Roblin (Jr.) and Clapp, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4890.
3. Friedberg *et al.*, *J. Clin. Invest.*, 1952, 31, 1074.
4. B. P. 639, 281/1953; *Chem. Abst.*, 1954, 48, 4584.
5. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 2nd ed., 1960, p. 806.

The 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been prepared by cyclisation of the appropriate aroylthiosemicarbazides, following the method of Maffii *et al*⁶. The required aroylthiosemicarbazides were obtained by the reaction of aroylhydrazines with NH_4SCN ⁷.

The substituted 2-aminothiadiazoles, when condensed in pyridine solution with acetyl sulphanyl chloride⁸, afforded 2-(*N*⁴-acetylsulphanilamido)thiadiazoles, which were hydrolysed to the corresponding 2-sulphanilamidothiadiazoles. These sulphthiadiazoles were fused with phthalic and succinic anhydrides in glacial acetic acid⁴ and the corresponding 2-(*N*⁴-phthalyl)- and 2-(*N*⁴-succinyl)-sulphthiadiazoles obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

Aroylthiosemicarbazides were prepared according to the method of Lora-Tamayo *et al*⁷. The appropriate acid hydrazide hydrochloride (0.1*M*) [obtained from the appropriate ester (0.4*M*) and hydrazine hydrate (0.6*M*)] was refluxed with NH_4SCN (10 g.) in ethanolic solution for 4 to 8 hr. The solution was cooled and the aroylthiosemicarbazide isolated in the usual way. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

S.No.	R.	M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Fluoro-	150°	50	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ON}_3\text{FS}$	14.88	15.04
2	2-Chloro-	205°	45	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ON}_3\text{ClS}$	13.40	13.96
3	2-Iodo-5-bromo-	175°	52	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{ON}_3\text{BrIS}$	7.99	8.01
4	2-Iodo-3,5-dibromo-	168-70°	54	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{ON}_3\text{Br}_2\text{IS}$	6.40	6.69
5	2-Nitro-	210° ^a	60	...	..	..
6	4-Nitro-	214° ^a	50	..	..	..
7	3-Nitro-	212-15°	45	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$	13.58	13.34
8	4-Methoxy-	236° ^b	48	...	...	...

^a-Masakiohta *et al.*, *Chem. Abst.*, 1953, 47, 9424, report the same m.p.

^b-Lit (*Chem. Abst.*, 1949, 43, 1163) records the same m.p.

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles.—The aroylthiosemicarbazide (0.1*M*) was treated dropwise with H_2SO_4 (conc., 10ml); the mixture was cooled and poured into water. On neutralisation with ammonia, the thiadiazole compound was precipitated. It was filtered and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The m.p., yields, and analytical data of various 2-amino-substituted thiadiazoles are recorded in Table II

2-(N⁴-Acetylsulphanilamido)-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles.—The 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.1*M*), dissolved in freshly distilled pyridine, was treated with a solution of *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride (0.1*M*) in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for 1 to 2 hr. and then poured on water. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

2-Sulphanilamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles.—The 2-(*N*⁴-acetylsulphanilamido)thiadiazole (4 g.), obtained as above, was refluxed with 10-12% HCl (16ml) for 2 hr. The

6. *Chem. Abst.*, 1950, 53, 2211.

7. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1962, 1020.

8. Masakiohta *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1951, 71, 1491.

mixture was poured on equal volume of water, boiled, and filtered. The filtrate on neutralisation with sodium carbonate provided the desired product. In certain cases, the hydrolysis was best achieved with NaOH (10%). In such cases neutralisation with dilute acetic acid furnished the required sulphathiadiazole compound.

The condensation products of *p*-acetamidobenzenesulphonyl chloride with various 2-aminothiadiazoles and their corresponding amino compounds are recorded in Table III.

TABLE II

*S.No.	M.P.		%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
	Obs.	Lit.			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1	211°	..	58	C ₈ H ₆ N ₃ FS	21.32	21.02	15.58	15.92
2	184-86°	184°	50	C ₈ H ₆ N ₃ ClS	..	..	14.84	14.74
3	184°	..	60	C ₈ H ₅ N ₃ BrIS	10.80	10.99	8.22	8.37
4	115°	..	61	C ₈ H ₄ N ₃ Br ₂ IS	8.98	9.11	6.42	6.94
6	234°	234°	61	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	14.40	14.41
6	256°	260°	58	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	14.44	14.41
7	230°	230°	54	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	..	..	14.47	14.41
8	188°	190°	56	C ₈ H ₆ ON ₃ S	..	..	14.88	15.45

*R is serially the same as in Table I.

TABLE III

*S.No.	M.P.	%Yield	% Sulphur.		M.P.	Yield.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
			<i>p</i> -Acetamido derivatives.				<i>p</i> -Amino derivatives.	
1	204°	48	16.44	16.93	133°	50	18.84	18.28
2	178°	50	16.22	16.24	159°	42	17.22	17.43
3	170-75°	60	10.88	11.32	190.94°	44	11.32	11.91
4	91°	70	9.94	9.93	75°	54	10.24	10.38
5	200°	44	15.44	15.80	190°	45	16.00	16.32
6	192°	50	15.40	15.80	148°	54	16.12	16.32
7	270°	48	15.42	15.80	154°	50	16.22	16.32
8	220°	30	16.80	16.41	230°	20	16.44	17.66

*R is serially the same as in Tables I and II.

2-(*N*⁴-Phthalylsulphanilamido)-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles.—A mixture of phthalic anhydride (0.01*M*), 2-sulphanilamidothiadiazole (0.01*M*) and glacial acetic acid (3*M*) was boiled for ½ hr. The product was poured on water, cooled, and filtered; the precipitate was washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from water-ethanol mixture. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

R.	M.P.	%Yield.	% Sulphur.		M.P.	%Yield.	% Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.			Found.	Reqd.
			Phthalyl derivatives (structure IV).				Succinyl derivatives (structure V).	
4-Fluoro	166°	50	12.44	12.85	108°	50	14.42	14.22
2-Chloro	154-56°	60	12.24	12.44	168-70°	60	13.32	13.72
2-Iodo-5-bromo	178°	54	9.20	9.34	110-15°	52	10.14	10.04
2-Iodo-3,5-dibromo	196°	50	8.12	8.34	148°	50	8.44	8.93
3-Nitro	180°	52	12.44	12.67	102°	56	12.78	13.42
4-Nitro	..	..	..	..	270°(d)	52	12.80	12.42

d: melts with decomposition.

2, (N⁺-Succinylsulphanilamido)-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared by exactly the similar procedure from succinic anhydride and other components taken in the same proportions as above. The compounds were recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. These are recorded in Table IV.

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